

World News of Natural Sciences

An International Scientific Journal

WNOFNS 60 (2025) 455-465

EISSN 2543-5426

Characterization and Application of Activated Carbon from African Star Apple (*Chrysophyllum albidum* G.Don) Seed Testa in the Adsorption of Eosin Red (ER) from Industrial Wastewater

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ABSTRACT

Wastewater from textile industries is often discharged into the environment, negatively impacting both aquatic and terrestrial life, as well as the aesthetic value of the surroundings. This research evaluates the activated carbon from star apple seed testa and its application in removing the cationic dye eosin red from wastewater. The Langmuir and Freundlich models were employed to evaluate the adsorption isotherms. The results indicate that adsorption efficiency increases with longer contact time and higher adsorbent doses, while it decreases with higher adsorbent concentration. Furthermore, the adsorption of eosin red dye by the activated carbon prepared from star apple seed testa follows the Freundlich isotherm model, indicating that the surface of the adsorbent is heterogeneous.

Keywords: Activated Carbon, African Star Apple, Seed Testa, Eosin Red, Wastewater

1. INTRODUCTION

Textile industries are significant water consumers, generating a substantial volume of effluents daily at various stages of textile processing (Thamaraiselvan and Noel, 2015; Nagaraju *et al.*, 2016). Major environmental problems are brought on by water contamination nowadays. This causes a health risk for humans and other organisms that use the water, as well as a decrease in the amount of oxygen in the water, which impacts the sustainability of animal life because oxygen is required for aquatic plant photosynthesis (Lakshmi *et al.*, 2018; Memon *et al.*, 2020).

Several kinds of hazardous compounds were found in textile wastewater, with an average daily discharge of 200 L/kg of fabric (Kant, 2012; Holkar *et al.*, 2016). When released directly into the environment or water, some textile dyes have the potential to have negative, long-lasting consequences on ecosystems (Robinson *et al.*, 2001). Therefore, it is crucial to remove these colors from industrial effluents before releasing them into the environment.

Activated carbon (AC) is a highly effective adsorbent commonly used for wastewater treatment, thanks to its large surface area, high porosity, and strong adsorption capacity. It has been considered a common adsorbent appropriate for removing numerous contaminants because of its high capacity and adaptability; however, the cost of this adsorbent occasionally restricts its broad use and makes it commercially undesirable (Crini *et al.*, 2019). An excellent adsorbent should possess an appropriate amount of capacity together with a large surface area, exhibiting both thermal and chemical stability.

It should be readily accessible, cheap, sustainable, and easily regenerated, while also demonstrating high selectivity for the target substances. It can be produced from various carbon-rich materials, including agricultural waste. Recently, there has been an increasing demand for eco-friendly and cost-effective adsorbents, sparking research into using agricultural by-products for activated carbon production.

One such promising material is the seed testa (the outer covering) of the African star apple (*Chrysophyllum albidum*). This indigenous fruit tree is prevalent in West Africa, and its seeds are usually discarded as waste. However, the seed testa contains significant amounts of lignin and cellulose, which make it suitable for conversion into activated carbon. Utilizing agricultural waste for adsorbent production aligns with principles of sustainability and waste valorization (Adebayo *et al.*, 2017).

Activated carbon derived from the testa of the African star apple seed can be effectively used to adsorb various pollutants, including dyes such as Eosin Red (ER). Eosin Red is a synthetic dye commonly used in the textile, paper, and pharmaceutical industries. Its presence in wastewater raises significant environmental concerns due to its toxicity and potential harm to aquatic life. Therefore, effective removal of Eosin Red from wastewater is crucial for reducing its environmental impact (Olukanni *et al.*, 2019).

The adsorption process involves the adherence of dye molecules to the surface of the activated carbon, and its efficiency depends on several factors, including the surface characteristics of the adsorbent, pH, temperature, and contact time. Previous studies have shown that activated carbon derived from various agricultural wastes is effective in adsorbing dyes from aqueous solutions.

Thus, producing activated carbon from African star apple seed testa for the removal of Eosin Red presents a promising approach to both wastewater treatment and waste utilization (Bello *et al.*, 2021).

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2. 1. Materials

The chemicals used for this investigation and preparation of activated carbon were all analytical grade purity, and the solutions were prepared in distilled water. The chemicals used were Zinc Chloride ($ZnCl_2$), sodium hydroxide and methylene gentian violet and blue.

2. 2. Sample Collection

The seed testas of star apple were bought from Itam market, and the seed testa was separated from the fruit pulp using a knife. The samples were cut into ships of workable size.

2. 3. Activation-Carbonization

Zinc chloride ($ZnCl_2$) was used as an activating agent. 100g of the sample chips were shocked in 1000 ml of 1M solution of $ZnCl_2$, this gives the ratio of sample to activating chemical of 1:10. The mixture was thoroughly mixed and heated until all the activating liquor was absorbed by the sample. It was then charred in the furnace at 500 °C for 2 hours.

The sample was then removed from the furnace and cooled in the desiccator, It was then washed with 0.5M NaOH followed by distilled water to a neutral pH. The activated carbons obtained were dried in the oven at 100 °C to a constant weight.

2. 4. Characterization of the Activated Carbon

Percentage Yield: The yield of the activated carbon was calculated using;

$$\text{Percentage yield (\%)} = \frac{M_2}{M_1} \times 100\%$$

where: M_1 = Weight of the sample, M_2 = Weight of the activated carbon

Moisture content: The Moisture content of the activating carbon was calculated using

$$\text{Percentage moisture content (\%)} = \frac{M_1 - M_2}{M_1} \times 100\%$$

where M_1 = Weight of the activated carbon before drying in the oven, M_2 = Weight of the activated carbon after drying in the oven

Determination of Ash content: The Ash content of the activated carbon was determined as follows: 2g of each activated carbon were put in a crucible and fired at 900 °C in a muffle furnace for 3 hours. The resultant ash was removed and allowed to cool in the desiccator.

Ash content was calculated using:

$$\text{Ash content (\%)} = \frac{W_2}{W_1} \times 100\%$$

where W_2 = Weight of the ash, W_1 = Weight of the activated carbon.

2. 5. Adsorption Study

The adsorption potentials of the activated carbon obtained were determined according to the method reported by Okeola & Odebunmi (2010). In this method, batch adsorption experiments were carried out at room temperature.

2. 5. 1. Adsorption Procedure

A simulated dye solution of eosin red with a concentration of 250 mg/L was prepared as a standard stock solution. This was carried out by dissolving 0.25 mg of eosin red in 1000 mL of distilled water. Different concentrations of eosin red were subsequently prepared by dilution when necessary. All the sorption experiments were carried out at room temperature.

2. 5. 2. Equilibrium Studies

Equilibrium studies were carried out to evaluate the effect of adsorbent dosage, adsorbate concentration and contact time. The post-adsorption concentrations of the dye solutions were analyzed using- visible spectrophotometer. All measurements were made at the wavelength corresponding to maximum adsorption ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 514 \text{ nm}$).

2. 5. 3. Effect of Adsorbent Dosage on Dye Adsorption

The effect of the activated carbon dose on the equilibrium uptake of the eosin red was investigated with various quantities of the adsorbent (0.1g-0.5g) in 50 ml of 100 mg/L of the dye solution(s). The contact time was 24 hours.

2. 5. 4. Effect of Dye Concentration

The adsorption experiment was carried out by adding a fixed amount of the activated carbon (0.2g) into 50 mL of different concentrations of dye solution (50 – 250 mg/L). The mixture was kept for 24 hours before filtering

2. 5. 5. Effect of Contact Time

The adsorption experiment was carried out by adding a fixed amount of the adsorbent (0.2g) into 50 mL of 100 mg/L of the dye solution. This was carried out in 5 different plastics bottles. The mixture was filtered after 24, 48, 76, 90, and 120 hours.

2. 5. 6. Data Analysis

From the UV-Visible absorbance results obtained, post-adsorption concentrations were determined using the Beer-Lambert's equation

$$A = EbC$$

where: A is the absorbance, E is the molar absorptivity, b is the path length, and C is the concentration of the adsorbate. The above equation was further substituted to arrive at:

$$\frac{A_1}{A_2} = \frac{C_1}{C_2}$$

where: A_1 is the pre-absorbance and A_2 is the post-absorbance of the dye, C_1 is the pre-adsorption concentration, and C_2 is the post-adsorption concentration. Therefore, we arrived at $C_2 =$ which is the required equation.

The percentage of the dye adsorbed and adsorption efficiency were determined for each sample of activated carbon at the same equilibrium points. Adsorption efficiency/capacity was calculated using:

$$\text{Adsorption efficiency (\%)} = \frac{(C_0 - C)}{C_0} \times 100\%$$

The amount of solute uptake per unit mass of activated carbon q_e (mg/g) was calculated using adsorption system mass balance given as:

$$q_e = \frac{v(c_i - c_f)}{m}$$

where: V = volume of the dye solution (m/l), m = amount of dry adsorbent (g), C_i = initial concentration (mg/L) and C_f = final concentration (g)

Determination of adsorption isotherm

Equilibrium adsorption isotherms are used to show the relationship between adsorbate concentration in solution and the amount of the adsorbent at equilibrium. Isotherm models provide fundamental information on the sorption mechanism and heterogeneity of the adsorbent. The isotherm models determined in this work are the Langmuir and Freundlich isotherms.

Langmuir isotherm: This isotherm model describes monolayer adsorption onto the surface of an adsorbent with a finite number of identical adsorption sites. It assumes that adsorption occurs at specific homogenous sites within the adsorbent and no interaction between the adsorbent sites, the model is expressed as

$$\frac{1}{q_e} = \frac{1}{q_{max}} + \frac{1}{q_{max}K_L} \cdot \frac{1}{C_e}$$

where: q_e is the quantity of dye adsorbed in (mg/g) at equilibrium. It corresponds to complete monolayer coverage. C_e is the equilibrium concentration of the adsorbate (mg/L), K_L is the Langmuir constant related to the energy of the adsorption (L/mg), and q_{max} is the maximum sorption of the adsorbate from the solution (mg/g). q_{max} and K_L were determined from the intercept and slope of the plot of $1/q_e$ against $1/C_e$

From Langmuir isotherm, R_L values were obtained, which are expressed as

$$R_L = \frac{1}{1 + K_L C_0}$$

Adsorption is said to be favorable if $0 < R_L < 1$ and unfavorable if $R_L > 1$

Freundlich Isotherm: Freundlich isotherm is an empirical equation used to describe the heterogeneity of the adsorbent surface, which is an indication that the binding sites are not equivalent or dependent.

The linear form of the equation is given as

$$\log q_e = \log K_f + 1/n \log C_e$$

where: q_e is the quantity of the adsorbate adsorbed at equilibrium (mg/g), C_e is the equilibrium concentration of the adsorbate (mg/L), K_f is the empirical constant that indicates the overall adsorption capacity (mg/g). $1/n$ is a dimensionless quantity; it is the sorption intensity of adsorbate into adsorbent or surface heterogeneity. The value of $1/n$ ranges from 0-1, and the closer the value is to zero, the more heterogeneous the adsorbent surface (Okeola *et al.*, 2014).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3. 1. Physical parameters of the activated carbon

The percentage yield, ash content, and moisture content of the activated carbon are presented in Table 1. These parameters are factors which could influence the adsorption capacity of the activated carbon (Okeola *et al.*, 2011). The ash content compares favorably with those for the commercial activated carbon and with that of H_3PO_4 , $ZnCl_2$, and KOH -activated carbon from maize cob reported by Okeola and Odebunnin (2010) and $NaCl$ -activated carbon of *Jatropha curcas* seed coats reported by Okeola *et al.* (2011). The moisture content of the activated carbon was higher, which implies that the $ZnCl_2$ -activated carbon has a greater pore size for absorption.

Table 1. Physical parameters of the activated carbon.

Parameters	Percentage (%)
Yield	38.75
Moisture content	12.0
Ash content	16.5

3. 2. Adsorption Studies

This study aimed to evaluate the adsorption potential of activated carbon derived from star apple testa. The results of the adsorption of the cationic dye eosin red by the activated carbon are presented in Table 2. Additionally, the isotherm data can be found in Table 5 and Figures 1 and 2. The findings indicate that the amount of adsorbent significantly influences the adsorption of eosin red from aqueous solutions.

In order to understand the study, experimental data were fitted using the Langmuir and Freundlich isotherm models.

Figures 1 and 2 illustrates the plots corresponding to these isotherm models. As surface coverage increases, the isotherm predicts a consistent decrease in heat of adsorption (ΔH_{ads}) for interlayer molecules, suggesting interactions between adsorbate and sorbent. This supports a heterogeneous surface concept, with adsorption energy decreasing as coverage increases (Patriota *et al.*, 2020). The Langmuir model, with a R^2 value of 0.9832, can also aptly describe ER sorption onto the adsorbent while the Freundlich model with a R^2 0.9891. This result was contrary to (Adaramola et al. 2024) which stated Langmuir model with a R^2 value of 0.989. The Langmuir model postulates that the adsorption took place on a uniform surface of the natural adsorbent, with a limited quantity of identical and independent adsorption sites (Adaramola et al. 2024).

This result showed a slight decrease with the Langmuir model of (Umoren et al. 2023) which stated Langmuir model showing highest data, $R^2 = 0.9940$ for Pb, whereas, the Freundlich isotherm showed highest $R^2 = 0.9548$ for Cd. The Freundlich model is known for its versatility and ability to describe multilayer adsorption on heterogeneous surfaces, making it suitable for complex adsorption processes involving clay samples and heavy metals (Andy and Toro-Vazquez, 2009). The Langmuir isotherm assumes a monolayer adsorption with a limited number of identical sites. Inconsistencies in their performance may be attributed to variations in the surface characteristics and adsorption mechanisms of the clay samples and heavy metals (Christianah, *et al.*, 2009).

The results indicate that adsorption efficiency increases with a higher mass of the adsorbent. As the mass of the adsorbent increases, the contact surface area of the adsorbent particles also rises. This larger surface area means that it is more likely for solute or dye molecules to adsorb onto the adsorption sites, thereby enhancing adsorption efficiency (Ayranci and Duman, 2005; Okeola *et al.*, 2012).

Additionally, the concentration of the adsorbate significantly affects the adsorption capacity of activated carbon. It was observed that adsorption efficiency decreases as the concentration of the adsorbate increases. At lower concentrations, there are sufficient active sites on the adsorbent for the adsorbate to occupy easily (Nsi *et al.*, 2016). However, as the concentration rises, many of the active sites on the adsorbent become masked by the adsorbate molecules, leading to a decrease in adsorption capacity. Once all active sites are masked, the adsorption process ceases.

Table 2. Effect of adsorbent dosage on the Adsorption of Eosin red (ER) by activated carbon prepared from star apple.

AC dosage (mg)	Post Adsorption Conc. (Mg/l)	Adsorption efficiency (%)
100	67.67	32.33
200	46.92	53.08
300	45.34	54.66
400	43.65	56.35
500	42.63	57.37

Table 3. Effect of contact time on the adsorption of ER.

Contact time (Hours)	Post Adsorption Conc. of (Mg/l)	Adsorption Efficiency (%)
24	66.45	33.55
48	46.95	53.05
72	40.40	59.60
96	36.09	63.91
120	35.05	64.95

Table 4. Effect of adsorbate concentration.

Adsorbate conc. (mg/L)	Post adsorption conc. (mg/L)	Adsorption efficiency (%)
50	7.61	84.78
100	39.95	60.05
150	89.35	40.43
200	165.34	17.33
250	208.10	16.80

Table 5. Isotherm data for the adsorption of eosin red using star apple-activated carbon.

Ce	Qe	1/ce	1/qe	Log Ce	Log qe
67.67	16165	0.0147	0.0000618	1.8304	4.208
46.92	13270	0.0213	0.0000753	1.6713	4.123
45.34	9100	0.0220	0.000109	1.6565	3.959
43.65	7043	0.0229	0.000142	1.6399	3.848
42.63	5737	0.0235	0.000174	1.6297	3.758

The adsorption of Eosin Red onto activated carbon derived from star apple seed testa shows a good fit for both Langmuir and Freundlich adsorption isotherms. The linear regression

values (R^2) were 0.9832 for the Langmuir isotherm and 0.9891 for the Freundlich isotherm. These values are relatively close to one, indicating that the adsorbent is suitable for this particular adsorbate. However, the Freundlich isotherm provided a better fit than the Langmuir isotherm, suggesting that the surface of the adsorbent is heterogeneous.

Figure 1. Langmuir isotherm plot for the adsorption of ER.

Figure 2. Freundlich isotherm plot for the adsorption of ER.

4. CONCLUSION

Star apple seed testas were successfully converted into activated carbon using $ZnCl_2$ as the activating agent. The physical properties of the resulting activated carbon were found to compare favorably with those of commercially available activated carbon. The adsorption capacity increased with higher adsorbent dosage and longer contact time but decreased with higher dye concentration. The adsorption of eosin red from simulated wastewater using star apple testa-activated carbon followed the Freundlich isotherm model, indicating that the surface of the activated carbon prepared from the star apple was heterogeneous.

Recommendation

Based on the findings of the study conducted, the following recommendations emerge: It is advisable to produce activated carbon from the testa of the star apple, harnessing its potential for the treatment of wastewater generated by textile industries. The influence of various factors, such as the pH level of the adsorbate, the type of activating agent employed, and the impregnation ratio, should be thoroughly investigated to optimise the effectiveness of the star apple testa-derived activated carbon. Additionally, a comprehensive evaluation of the kinetics of the adsorption process is essential to better understand its dynamics and efficiency.

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